

A remark on embedding of a cylinder on a real commutative Banach algebra

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Abstract:

Let A be a real commutative Banach algebra with unity. Let $a_0 \in A \setminus \{0\}$. Let $\mathbb{Z}a_0 := \{na_0\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$. Then, $\mathbb{Z}a_0$ is a discrete subgroup of A . For any $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the Frechet derivative of the mapping

$$x \in A \quad \mapsto \quad x + na_0 \in A$$

is the identity map on A and, especially, an A -linear transformation on A . So, the quotient group $A/(\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ is a 1-dimensional A -manifold and the covering projection

$$x \in A \quad \mapsto \quad x + \mathbb{Z}a_0 \in A/(\mathbb{Z}a_0)$$

is an A -map. We call $A/(\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ the 1-dimensional A -cylinder by a_0 .

Let T be a compact Hausdorff space. Suppose that there exist $t_1 \in T$ and $t_2 \in T$ such that $t_1 \neq t_2$ holds. Then, the set $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ of all real-valued continuous functions on T is a real commutative Banach algebra with unity and $\mathbb{R} \subsetneq C(T; \mathbb{R})$ holds. In this paper, we show that there exists $a_0 \in C(T; \mathbb{R}) \setminus \mathbb{R}$ such that for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the 1-dimensional $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -cylinder $(C(T; \mathbb{R}))/(\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ by a_0 cannot be embedded in the finite direct product space $(C(T; \mathbb{R}))^k$ as a $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold.

Keywords: immersion, isotopy, bump function, partition of unity, Gelfand representation, Radon measure, von Neumann algebra, C^* -algebra, Serre-Swan theorem, complex vector bundle, locally trivial fiber space, infinite-dimensional Lie group, Cartesian product, Euclidean space, Affine space, vector sheaf.

In this paper, we give a remark concerned with an A -manifold (a manifold on a commutative topological algebra A). There are already various studies related to A -manifolds or their analogues (e.g., [1], [2], \dots , [9]). In [10], we showed the existence of a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -manifold that cannot be embedded in the finite-dimensional Affine space $(C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}))^k$ as a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold. In this paper, we show the following existence theorem, which is a generalization.

Theorem : Let T be a compact Hausdorff space. Suppose that there exist $t_1 \in T$ and $t_2 \in T$ such that $t_1 \neq t_2$ holds. Then, there exists $a_0 \in C(T; \mathbb{R}) \setminus \mathbb{R}$ such that for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the cylinder $(C(T; \mathbb{R})) / (\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ cannot be embedded in the Cartesian product $(C(T; \mathbb{R}))^k$ as a $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold.

Proof : Because T is normal, by Urysohn's lemma, there exists $a_0 \in C(T; \mathbb{R}) \setminus \mathbb{R}$ such that $a_0(t_1) = -1$ and $a_0(t_2) = +1$ hold. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, by a contradiction, we show that $(C(T; \mathbb{R})) / (\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ cannot be embedded in $(C(T; \mathbb{R}))^k$ as a $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold.

Suppose that $(C(T; \mathbb{R})) / (\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ can be embedded in $(C(T; \mathbb{R}))^k$ as a $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold. Then, there exists a $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -injection Ψ from $(C(T; \mathbb{R})) / (\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ to $(C(T; \mathbb{R}))^k$. Let

$$(1) \quad b_0(t) := \max\{0, a_0(t)\} \quad (t \in T).$$

Then, $b_0 \in C(T; \mathbb{R})$ and

$$[0] = [a_0] \neq [b_0]$$

hold, where $[x]$ denotes the equivalence class of $x \in C(T; \mathbb{R})$. That is, we put

$$[x] := x + \mathbb{Z}a_0 \quad (x \in C(T; \mathbb{R})).$$

So, because $\Psi([0]) = \Psi([a_0]) \neq \Psi([b_0])$ holds, there exists $l_0 \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ such that

$$(2) \quad \Psi_{l_0}([0]) = \Psi_{l_0}([a_0]) \neq \Psi_{l_0}([b_0])$$

holds, where Ψ_{l_0} denotes the l_0 -th component of Ψ . Then, because Ψ is a $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -injection from $(C(T; \mathbb{R})) / (\mathbb{Z}a_0)$ to $(C(T; \mathbb{R}))^k$, as we put

$$\Phi(x) := \Psi_{l_0}([x]) \quad (x \in C(T; \mathbb{R})),$$

the map

$$x \in C(T; \mathbb{R}) \quad \mapsto \quad \Phi(x) \in C(T; \mathbb{R})$$

is a $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -map and, especially, Frechet derivatives of Φ are $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ -linear transformations on $C(T; \mathbb{R})$. That is,

$$(3) \quad \Phi'(x) \in C(T; \mathbb{R}) \quad (x \in C(T; \mathbb{R}))$$

holds, because, in general, if A is a commutative ring with the unity 1_A and L is an A -linear transformation on A , then

$$L(1_A) \in A$$

and

$$L(x) = L(x \cdot 1_A) = x \cdot (L(1_A)) = (L(1_A)) \cdot x \quad (x \in A)$$

hold. Now, from (2), there exists $t_0 \in T$ such that

$$(4) \quad (\Phi(0))(t_0) = (\Phi(a_0))(t_0) \neq (\Phi(b_0))(t_0)$$

holds. Then, from (1), Case 1 : “ $0 = b_0(t_0)$ ” or Case 2 : “ $a_0(t_0) = b_0(t_0)$ ” holds.

First, we consider Case 1. Let $0 = b_0(t_0)$. Let

$$F_1(s) := sb_0 \quad (s \in [0, 1]).$$

Then, the map

$$s \in [0, 1] \mapsto F_1(s) \in C(T; \mathbb{R})$$

is a line from 0 to b_0 in $C(T; \mathbb{R})$ and

$$(F_1)'(s) = b_0 \quad (s \in [0, 1])$$

holds. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi(b_0) - \Phi(0) \\ &= \Phi(F_1(1)) - \Phi(F_1(0)) \\ &= \int_0^1 (\Phi'(F_1(s))) ((F_1)'(s)) ds \\ &= \int_0^1 (\Phi'(F_1(s))) b_0 ds \end{aligned}$$

holds. So, in virtue of (3), for any $t \in T$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\Phi(b_0))(t) - (\Phi(0))(t) \\
&= \int_0^1 ((\Phi'(F_1(s))) b_0)(t) ds \\
&= \int_0^1 ((\Phi'(F_1(s)))(t)) \cdot (b_0(t)) ds
\end{aligned}$$

holds. However, because of $0 = b_0(t_0)$,

$$(\Phi(b_0))(t_0) - (\Phi(0))(t_0) = 0$$

holds. It contradicts (4).

Next, we consider Case 2. Let $a_0(t_0) = b_0(t_0)$. Let

$$F_2(s) := a_0 + s(b_0 - a_0) \quad (s \in [0, 1]).$$

Then, similarly, because

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Phi(b_0) - \Phi(a_0) \\
&= \int_0^1 (\Phi'(F_2(s))) (b_0 - a_0) ds
\end{aligned}$$

holds, in virtue of (3) and $a_0(t_0) = b_0(t_0)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\Phi(b_0))(t_0) - (\Phi(a_0))(t_0) \\
&= \int_0^1 ((\Phi'(F_2(s)))(t_0)) \cdot (b_0(t_0) - a_0(t_0)) ds \\
&= 0
\end{aligned}$$

holds. It contradicts (4). ■

Comment : Kasuya suggested that an \mathbb{R}^n -manifold and a \mathbb{C}^n -manifold might be related to a differential web and a holomorphic web, respectively. He proposed a candidate for a compact \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold N such that for any \mathbb{C} -manifolds M_1 and M_2 , N can not be embedded in $M_1 \times M_2$ as a \mathbb{C}^2 -submanifold. The construction of our example was inspired by this proposal. —

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